

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF OLEFIN-BASED COMPOSITE MATERIALS FILLED WITH RECYCLED CARBON FIBRES FOR 3D PRINTING APPLICATION

Corrado Sciancalepore^{1,*}, Antonio Panico¹, Matteo Leonardi¹, Luca Collini¹, Paolo Albertelli², Valerio Mussi², Daniel Milanese¹

¹ *DISTI, Department of Industrial Systems and Technologies, University of Parma, Parco area delle Scienze 181/A, 43124 Parma, Italy*

corrado.sciancalepore@unipr.it

antonio.panico@unipr.it

matteo.leonardi@studenti.unipr.it

luca.collini@unipr.it

daniel.milanese@unipr.it

² *MUSP Consortium, Machine tools and production systems, Via Vittore Callegari 21/F 29122 Piacenza, Italy*

paolo.albertelli@polimi.it

valerio.mussi@musp.net

Keywords: Composite materials, polypropylene, recycled carbon fiber, 3D printing

ABSTRACT

The composites industry is experiencing steady growth worldwide. However, the recycling of composite fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) materials, which make up a significant proportion of composite materials used in engineering applications, is still a challenge. The process of recycling the high value fiber part of thermoset materials requires ad hoc processes for the recovery (mechanical, thermal or chemical process) and reuse of this valuable resource.

The work presented, based on recycled carbon fiber, evaluates the possibility of transforming the recycled fiber into a new thermoplastic composite material through a technological approach of extrusion and then using the material obtained through injection molding and 3D printing, promoting the adoption of a circular and innovative approach to the recycling of composite materials.

In particular, the recycled carbon fibers (fillers) were ground to obtain short fibers and characterized by particle size and electron microscopy. The filler was compounded with the thermoplastic matrix (polypropylene) by twin-screw extrusion.

The extrusion of the composite material took place in the form of a filament that was collected on reels and pelletized into granules. Characterization of the mechanical properties of the composite material was carried out by means of tensile tests on standard specimens (type 5A) according to ISO 527, obtained by injection molding. Finally, the pellets were used as raw material in an additive fused granules fabrication process and the printed objects were further characterized after 3D printing.

The process of transforming and obtaining materials in terms of mechanical and thermal properties has been optimized, comparing them with those of unfilled virgin materials.

In addition, recycled carbon fibers were valorized by upcycling them as structural fillers for polymer matrix composites, with a view to a sustainable circular economy.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the growing demand for lightweight, high-performance materials in industries such as aerospace, automotive, and sports has highlighted the critical role of carbon fiber-reinforced polymers

(CFRPs) due to their exceptional strength-to-weight ratio and durability [1]. However, these materials unfortunately face a significant challenge: the environmental and economic cost associated with their end-of-life disposal. Landfilling remains the predominant disposal method to date, exacerbating environmental issues and contradicting modern sustainability goals [2].

One possible and virtuous way to overcome this problem is through the reuse of recycled carbon fibers (rCF), obtained from waste CFRP components, as reinforcement in new composite materials [3-5]. This work shows the feasibility of incorporating pyrolysis-recovered rCFs into a polypropylene (PP) matrix to develop composite materials that combine sustainability and mechanical performance. In addition, the use of polypropylene grafted with maleic anhydride (PP-g-MA) as a compatibilizer is evaluated to improve interactions at the interface between the fibers and the polymer matrix and implement mechanical performance accordingly. The composite materials are processed by both traditional injection molding and fused granules fabrication (FGF) 3D printing, allowing comparison of different manufacturing techniques.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The starting polymer matrix is PP (Moplen HP456J), chosen for its mechanical versatility, chemical resistance and cost-effectiveness. However, its nonpolar and low surface energy characteristics may hinder compatibility with rCFs, necessitating the use of PP-g-MA to improve wettability at the interface. Carbon fibers recycled by pyrolysis (Carbiso), retain remarkable mechanical properties (tensile strength up to 5 GPa, Young's modulus around 240 GPa). They were milled to achieve optimal homogeneous dispersion in powder form and their size distribution characterized by laser granulometry.

Six composite formulations were prepared: three with increasing content of rCF (10%, 20%, 30%-named PP-rCF10, PP-rCF20, and PP-rCF30, respectively) and two incorporating 10% rCF with 2.5% and 5% maleic anhydride-functionalized polypropylene (called PPPP-gMA2.5-rCF10 and PPPP-gMA5-rCF10, respectively), in addition to pure PP. The compounds were obtained with a twin-screw extruder, producing filaments that were then pelletized for further processing by injection molding, which provides high dimensional stability, and FGF 3D printing, which directly uses the granules to form objects layer by layer. The latter approach certainly offers greater freedom in making objects of complex shape, but it presents challenges related to the inherent anisotropy of the finished object. For both printing technologies dumbbell specimens were obtained and used for the subsequent characterizations. For FGF 3D printing it was essential to understand how the addition of fibers affects the adhesion between layers. For this reason, two configurations were prepared with two raster angles, 0° and 90° , indicating the alignment of the strands, respectively parallel and perpendicular to the tensile direction of the specimen.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Various analytical techniques were used to assess the structural and mechanical properties of the materials. Laser granulometry reveals a fairly wide size distribution of rCF (between 1 and 300 μm), with an average volumetric diameter of around 70 μm (Fig. 1(a)), while scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images confirm the typical size and morphology of carbon fibers, highlighting the presence of a certain surface roughness that could favor adhesion and mechanical interlocking (Fig. 1(b) and (c)).

Figure 1: Size distribution curve (a) and SEM images at different magnification (b) and (c) of rCF.

Figure 2: Optical and SEM images of specimen cross sections obtained by injection moulding (a), FGF 3D printing with a raster angle of 0° (b) and 90° (c). The letters in the inset of the optical pictures indicate the composition of the sample: a) pure PP, b) PP-rCF10, c) PP-rCF20, d) PP-rCF30, e) PPPP-gMA2.5-rCF10 and f) PPPP-gMA5-rCF10.

SEM images of the composite cross sections show the microstructure of the injection-molded and 3D-printed samples (Fig. 2 (a), (b) and (c)). The fibers are homogeneously dispersed and distributed in all samples: in particular, the fibers are oriented mainly along the direction of the molding flow. In maleic anhydride-compatible samples, the fibers are wet by the polymer matrix and are effectively incorporated in the PP. Maleic anhydride, when grafted onto the polymer chain, introduces polar groups (specifically, the anhydride ring) that can interact with hydroxyl, carboxylic or epoxy groups on the fiber surface, due to the partial oxidation of fiber carbon atom.

The results of the melt flow index (MFI) measurement show how the fiber content influences the processability of the composite (Fig. 3): increasing the rCF concentration leads to a reduction in the MFI [6], while the addition of PP-g-AM brings the melt flow behavior back to values closer to those of pure PP [7]: MFI increases when the compatibilizing agent is used because the improved interfacial adhesion reduces internal resistance to flow, promotes better fiber dispersion, and minimizes agglomeration, resulting in a more uniform, less viscous melt.

Figure 3: MFI values as a function of material composition.

However, the most critical insights are provided by the tensile tests. These are conducted on samples from injection molding and 3D printing processes, with the latter being further divided into 0° and 90° raster orientations to assess their anisotropy in terms of mechanical properties (Fig. 4 and 5).

Figure 4: Comparison of mechanical parameters between injection-molded and 3D-printed (with the raster angle of 0°) samples.

Tensile tests reveal that the addition of fibers substantially increases the stiffness of the composites [8]. For injection-molded samples, the Young's modulus increases from about 1350 MPa in pure PP to

over 3200 MPa in the composite at 30% rCF. Interestingly, the yield strength remains almost constant between the various compositions, suggesting that the fibers contribute mainly to stiffness rather than ultimate strength. However, a drastic decrease in ductility and toughness is observed at higher rCF contents, reflecting the transition from ductile to brittle fracture behavior.

Figure 5: Comparison of mechanical parameters between 3D-printed samples with the raster angle of 0 and 90°, respectively.

For 3D-printed samples, anisotropy plays a significant role. Samples printed at a raster angle of 0° (aligned with the tensile stress) show better mechanical performance than those printed at 90°, which yield to lower deformations due to weaker adhesion between the layers [4]. The addition of the compatibilizer (PP-g-MA) increases performance in both cases, with significant improvements in mechanical performance compared to the unfilled material [9], and reduces anisotropy compared to the composite filled with the same percentage of rCF. The use of PP-g-MA facilitates better dispersion and adhesion of the fibers, favoring the transfer of stresses from the matrix to the fiber and validating its role as a crucial additive in rCF-reinforced PP composites.

The Halpin-Tsai equations [10], widely used to estimate the modulus of composites based on volume fraction and geometry of the fibers, are applied to validate experimental data (Fig. 6). Specifically, for determining the elastic modulus of 3D short-fiber composites, the Lavengood-Goettler equation is also used, serving as a complementary empirical tool in these calculations [11]:

$$E_c = \frac{1}{5} E_{11} + \frac{4}{5} E_{22} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Equation 1 applies to randomly in space oriented short fiber composites where E_{11} and E_{22} are the longitudinal and transverse modulus of a unidirectional discontinuous fiber composite having the same volume fraction of fibers:

$$E_{11} = \frac{1+2\left(\frac{l_f}{2r_f}\right)\eta_L V_f}{1-\eta_L V_f} E_m \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$E_{22} = \frac{1+2\eta_T V_f}{1-\eta_T V_f} E_m \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where:

$$\eta_L = \frac{\frac{E_f}{E_m} - 1}{\frac{E_f}{E_m} + 2\left(\frac{l_f}{2r_f}\right)} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

$$\eta_T = \frac{\frac{E_f}{E_m} - 1}{\frac{E_f}{E_m} + 2} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where E_m is the elastic modulus of the PP matrix, E_f is the elastic modulus of the carbon fiber, l_f and r_f are length and radius of the fiber, V_f is the fiber volume fraction.

Figure 6: Comparison of Young's modulus values obtained with the Halpin-Tsai model, injection molded and 3D printed samples, respectively.

Using average fiber dimensions obtained from particle size and densities measured through helium pycnometry, theoretical moduli were calculated and found to be very similar to experimental results. This alignment strengthens the validity of the physical evidence and suggests that the behavior of the composite adheres to established mechanical models.

4. CONCLUSION

Experimental results demonstrate the technical feasibility of developing olefin-based composites reinforced with pyrolyzed rCF, highlighting the dual benefits of improving mechanical performance and promoting environmental sustainability through the circular use of high value engineering materials. The incorporation of PP-g-MA as a compatibilizer significantly reduces the compatibility problems typically encountered with PP and carbon fibers, thus expanding the potential application of these composites.

Injection molding remains the method of choice in terms of scalability and mechanical performance, but 3D printing via FGF shows promising results, particularly for prototyping and customized applications. Further research could focus on refining the 3D printing parameters to minimize anisotropy, which is in any case reduced with the use of the compatibilizer.

Ultimately, this work contributes to increasing knowledge aimed at closing the loop on composite materials, aligning with the broader goals of resource efficiency and sustainable engineering, with a view to processing scalability and production at industrial levels.

REFERENCES

- [1] U. K. Vaidya, K. K. Chawla, Processing of fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites, *International Materials Reviews*, **53**, 2008, pp. 185–218 (doi.org/10.1179/174328008X325223).

- [2] F. Meng, Y. Cui, S. Pickering, J. McKechnie, From aviation to aviation: Environmental and financial viability of closed-loop recycling of carbon fibre composite, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **200**, 2020, pp. 1-8 (doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2020.108362).
- [3] H. Junaedi, E. Albahkali, M. Baig, A. Dawood, A. Almajid, Ductile to Brittle Transition of Short Carbon Fiber-Reinforced Polypropylene Composites, *Advances in Polymer Technology*, 2020, pp. 1-10 (doi.org/10.1155/2020/6714097).
- [4] B. Almeshari, H. Junaedi, M. Baig, A. Almajid, Development of 3D printing short carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene composite filaments. *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, **24**, 2023, 16–26 (doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2023.02.198).
- [5] H. Cheng, M. Tang, J. Zhang, H. Wang, J. Zhou, Q. Wang, Z. Qian, Effects of rCF attributes and FDM-3D printing parameters on the mechanical properties of rCFRP, *Composites Part B: Engineering*, **270**, 2024, pp. 1-14 (doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2023.111122).
- [6] A. Ghanbari, S. Seyedin, S. A. Haddadi, Reinforcing potential of recycled carbon fibers in compatibilized polypropylene composites. *Journal of Polymer Research*, **28**, 2021, pp. 1-9 (doi.org/10.1007/s10965-021-02506-0).
- [7] M. Baig, B. Almeshari, A. Aabid, H. Junaedi, A. Almajid, Heliyon, *Heliyon* 10, 2024, pp. 1-16 (doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e30510).
- [8] T. Qiu, Z. Yang, L.H. Liang, Multiscale analysis of the mechanical properties and interface damage mechanisms of carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene composites, *Polymer Composites*, **46**, 2025, pp. 46:8307–8317 (DOI: 10.1002/pc.29494).
- [9] J. Jang, S.J. Youn, S.Y. Kim, M. Park, Effect of polypropylene-grafted-maleic anhydride content on physical properties of carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene composites, *Functional Composite and Structures*, **2**, 2020, pp. 1-8 (doi.org/10.1088/2631-6331/abd374).
- [10] Fu S-Y, Lauke B, Mai Y-W. *Science and engineering of short fibre-reinforced polymer composites*. Woodhead Publishing, 2019.
- [11] L.E. Nielsen, and R.F. Landel, *Mechanical Properties of Polymers and Composites*, Marcel Dekker, 1994.